

Machine Learning-Based Pregnancy Complications Risk Prediction Model for Women in Rural Communities: A Retrospective Cohort Study

ABSTRACT

All pregnancies bear risks and it is necessary to care for all expectant mothers during and after pregnancy. However, high-risk pregnancies necessitate more attention from the early stages to prevent and anticipate possible complications. With the recent ease in acquiring and storing large amounts of data digitally, it is now possible to use certain health-related predictors to determine the risk of pregnancy complications before they arise. The ability of machine learning (ML) models to learn complexities in data makes them better suited for this task than conventional statistical methods. In this study, we retrieved data from the University of California, Irvine (UCI) machine learning repository to train machine learning models for pregnancy risk prediction, dividing the pregnancies into three classes: low-risk, mid-risk, and high-risk. A total of six ML algorithms were used to make predictions on the dataset, including logistic regression, random forest, support vector classifier, k-nearest neighbours, decision tree, naive Bayes. The random forest model had the best performance, with an area under the ROC curve (AUC) score of 0.7. The use of maternal factors to predict pregnancy risk classes can facilitate pre-labour decisions and better management of pregnancy complications.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The United Nations (UN) has prioritized maternal health (UN). To focus on maternal health around the world, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were established in 2000, followed by the

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015 (Tomar, K. et al 2024). Any risk during pregnancy can be detrimental to the health of the mother and unborn child. Although all pregnancies bear risks and necessitate care, a high-risk pregnancy (HRP) always requires additional care during and after delivery (Cleveland Clinic, 2021). Depending on an expectant woman's medical history, any pregnancy may become high-risk as it progresses. High-risk pregnancies can be avoided if complications are identified early. Regular checkups before and during pregnancy help many women have a risk-free pregnancy and delivery free of significant complications (US National Institutes of Health, 2017). Common pregnancy-related problems include maternal depression, obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure, and anxiety. According to the World Health Organization (2023), a woman dies every two minutes due to high blood pressure or other pregnancy-related complications. This statistic highlights the risks women face during pregnancy, which can result in miscarriage or complications during the postpartum period. It is critical to monitor the data generated throughout the different phases of pregnancy from various perspectives. Fortunately, computational tools can help detect hidden patterns and predict common risk factors. For instance, predictive modelling, natural language processing, pattern recognition, and image processing are significant computational techniques used to analyze pregnancy-related data. Previous research has demonstrated that various maternal variables influence women's health and can lead to pregnancy instability (Bertini et al., 2022). Predicting pregnancy risk is a crucial component of prenatal care, as it allows healthcare providers to take proactive measures to manage and mitigate risks. Complications such as preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, and preterm birth can have serious consequences for both the mother and the child. Approximately 15% of pregnant women experience life-threatening issues requiring specialized care, and others may need substantial obstetric interventions to survive (World Health Organization, 2019). Traditional risk

assessment approaches frequently rely on clinical criteria and demographic data, which may not adequately capture the complexities of particular cases.

Machine learning (ML) has been developed to analyze a wide range of health data, including patient information from multi-omic methods, clinical, behavioural, environmental, and pharmaceutical data, and data from the biomedical literature (Hinton, 2018). ML can assist professionals to make decisions, reduce medical errors, and improve diagnostic accuracy, thereby decreasing their workload (Makary & Daniel, 2016). These techniques provide the ability to infer significant connections between data from diverse datasets that would otherwise be impossible to correlate (Darcy et al., 2016; Obermeyer & Emanuel, 2016).

In recent years, several studies have been conducted to predict certain risks during pregnancy and determine the most suitable birth method based on maternal characteristics. For instance, Pereira et al. (2015) used various supervised machine learning (ML) algorithms to predict the most appropriate delivery method among vaginal, cesarean, forceps, and vacuum delivery. Similarly, Chen et al. (2011) utilized Neural Network (NN) and Decision Tree (DT) algorithms to predict factors associated with preterm birth. In another study, Rawashdeh et al. (2020) employed Random Forest (RF), DT, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and NNs to predict the risk of premature birth. These studies demonstrate the application of different ML techniques, each showing varying levels of performance in predicting pregnancy outcomes.

Hybrid models leverage the strengths of multiple machine learning (ML) techniques to enhance predictive performance. For example, combining Feedforward Neural Networks (FNN) with Random Forests (RF) utilizes FNN's feature extraction capabilities and RF's classification robustness, making it a powerful solution for complex prediction tasks. In healthcare, ML is

increasingly employed to deliver precise and personalized predictions. Techniques such as logistic regression, support vector machines (SVM), and decision trees have been widely used to estimate risks for various medical conditions (Islam et al., 2020).

Integrating models like Logistic Regression, Random Forests, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Trees, and Naive Bayes can improve the accuracy and reliability of predictions related to pregnancy complications. This multi-algorithmic approach ensures a more robust analysis, enabling healthcare professionals to make better-informed decisions tailored to individual patients.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Source

The University of California, Irvine (UCI) machine learning repository provided the dataset for this investigation [1]. An IoT risk monitoring system was initially used to collect the data from a number of hospitals, community clinics, and maternal health care facilities in rural Bangladesh. Seven pregnancy predictors were included in the dataset: risk level, body temperature (in degrees Fahrenheit), blood sugar (in mmol/L), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (in mmHg and mmHg, respectively), age (in years), and heart rate (in beats per minute). These are all numerical variables.

2.2 Modeling Tools

The Google Colab application was used to develop the proposed models and evaluate their performance. It provides a cloud-based platform that supports Jupyter Notebooks, which are

commonly used for machine learning development. Google Colab offers all the necessary infrastructure, platforms, and tools required for conducting machine learning experiments. One of its key advantages is its support for popular machine learning libraries, including TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Scikit-learn, making it an ideal environment for both the development and testing of machine learning models.

2.3 Data Preprocessing

The quality of training data is a major determinant of how good our machine learning model will be. If the data is unreliable and contains a lot of redundant or irrelevant information, then the training algorithm will learn irrelevant details and generalize poorly on unseen data. Therefore, we took steps to ensure data quality in preparation for training, including:

- Removing duplicate rows to reduce noise and redundancy in the data
- Feature encoding: machine learning models can only work with numerical values. Therefore, it was necessary to transform the RiskLevel feature containing categorical values into numeric values (0 for low risk, 1 for mid-risk, and 2 for high risk).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with Python 3.10.12, Pandas 2.2.2 library, Scikit-learn 1.5.2, Matplotlib 3.8.0, and Seaborn 0.13.2. We developed models to predict three risk levels for pregnant women: low-risk, mid-risk and high-risk using select machine learning models: logistic regression, random forest, support vector classifier, k-nearest neighbours, decision tree, and naive Bayes. Since the presence of imbalanced classes can make a machine learning model biased

towards the majority class (Kuhle et al., 2018), we handled the class imbalance with the Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (SMOTE). The low-risk class (51.8% of the dataset) was significantly higher than the mid- and high-risk classes (23.4% and 24.8% respectively), and SMOTE was used to create synthetic samples of the minority classes by interpolation to balance the dataset.

Figure 1: Distribution of risk levels in the dataset before and after SMOTE

2.5 Machine Learning Models

Logistic regression uses the sigmoid function to transform the output of a linear regression function into categorical values, making it possible to predict classes (Boateng & Abaye). Each component (tree) of a **random forest** model is like a flowchart that splits data into smaller groups based on the input features. At the end of the splitting process, each tree gives a prediction of the class an instance belongs to. This combination of opinions from the different trees to produce a final answer (called majority voting) makes decision trees robust to noise in the input data (Rigatti, 2017). **Support vector classifiers** work by transforming data to a higher dimension where it is linearly separable. It then finds the best boundary (called a hyperplane) which separates the data into classes while maximizing the distance from the data points to itself (Pisner & Schnyer, 2020). **K-nearest neighbours** (KNN) models work by the intuitive method of assigning a new data point

to a class based on the classes of its nearest neighbours in the training set (Cunningham & Delany, 2021). **Decision trees** work by splitting the data into smaller groups continuously based on the input features until a final decision is reached. A group of decision trees working together on a problem makes a random forest model (Rigatti, 2017). The **naive bayes** algorithm calculates the probability that an instance belongs to each class separately based on the input features, and then chooses the class with the highest probability (Yang, 2018). We used the Scikit-learn library to implement all the models.

The data was randomly split into a training (80%) and test (20%) set. The parameters used for each model are presented in Table 1 and the metrics of model performance are presented in Table 2.

3.0 RESULTS

After dropping the 562 duplicate rows, a total of 452 rows were left for training and testing. This number increased to 702 after resampling with SMOTE. A majority of the women in this dataset were between ages 20 and 25, and the average age was 29. Calculating the correlation between the predictors and the target revealed a medium positive correlation between the target (risk of pregnancy complications) and blood sugar level. This indicates that diabetes could be a major risk factor for pregnancy complications. Further investigation with box plots reveals that the high-risk class has a higher mean value for blood sugar than the other classes, strengthening the initial hypothesis.

Figure 2: Correlation plot of features

Figure 3: Box plot of blood sugar levels by risk class

Investigating the relationship between age and risk levels revealed that a majority of both the high risk and low risk cases were among women between ages 21 and 30 (Figure 5). In general, women in this age group account for the majority of the population in this dataset, which is to be expected given that this age range represents the peak reproductive years for women. Many women in this age group therefore have fewer health problems and higher energy levels, accounting for a high

number of pregnancies, both low and high risk, in this class of women. The class with the second highest number of high-risk cases was for women between ages 10-20. The women in this category are in fact children and adolescents and may not be fully developed for child bearing. The lack of physical, emotional, and economic maturity among women in this group increases their risk of developing pregnancy complications and decreases the chances that they can afford proper healthcare to handle these complications.

Figure 4: Age distribution in the dataset

Figure 5: Age distribution by risk levels

The area under the ROC curve (AUC) gives the probability that a model will rank a positive example (a high-risk pregnancy in this case) higher than a negative example. As long as the data used for training is roughly balanced, the model with a greater AUC is generally a better model. From Figure 6, the random forest model had the highest AUC of 0.8, which can be attributed to its robustness to noise and overfitting achieved by averaging the predictions of many decision trees. Table 1 presents the hyperparameters of each model, and Table 2 presents their evaluation metrics.

Figure 6: ROC curve for the 6 trained models

Table 1: Model hyperparameters

Model Name	Model Parameters
Logistic regression	'C': 1.0, 'class_weight': None, 'dual': False, 'fit_intercept': True, 'intercept_scaling': 1, 'l1_ratio': None, 'max_iter': 100, 'multi_class': 'deprecated', 'n_jobs': None, 'penalty': 'l2', 'random_state': None, 'solver': 'lbfgs', 'tol': 0.0001, 'verbose': 0, 'warm_start': False
Random forest	'bootstrap': True, 'ccp_alpha': 0.0, 'class_weight': None, 'criterion': 'gini', 'max_depth': None, 'max_features': 'sqrt', 'max_leaf_nodes': None, 'max_samples': None, 'min_impurity_decrease': 0.0, 'min_samples_leaf': 1, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'min_weight_fraction_leaf': 0.0, 'monotonic_cst': None, 'n_estimators': 100, 'n_jobs': None, 'oob_score': False, 'random_state': None, 'verbose': 0, 'warm_start': False
Support vector classifier	'C': 1.0, 'break_ties': False, 'cache_size': 200, 'class_weight': None, 'coef0': 0.0, 'decision_function_shape': 'ovr', 'degree': 3, 'gamma': 'scale', 'kernel': 'rbf', 'max_iter': -1, 'probability': True, 'random_state': None, 'shrinking': True, 'tol': 0.001, 'verbose': False
K-nearest neighbours	'algorithm': 'auto', 'leaf_size': 30, 'metric': 'minkowski', 'metric_params': None, 'n_jobs': None, 'n_neighbors': 5, 'p': 2, 'weights': 'uniform'
Decision tree	'ccp_alpha': 0.0, 'class_weight': None, 'criterion': 'gini', 'max_depth': None, 'max_features': None, 'max_leaf_nodes': None, 'min_impurity_decrease': 0.0, 'min_samples_leaf': 1, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'min_weight_fraction_leaf': 0.0, 'monotonic_cst': None, 'random_state': None, 'splitter': 'best'
Naïve bayes	'priors': None, 'var_smoothing': 1e-09

Table 2: Model metrics and performance

Model	Accuracy	ROC-AUC	Precision			Recall			F1-Score		
			Class 0	Class 1	Class 2	Class 0	Class 1	Class 2	Class 0	Class 1	Class 2
Logistic regression	0.57	0.67	0.49	0.45	0.79	0.64	0.35	0.75	0.56	0.39	0.77
Random forest	0.74	0.80	0.68	0.70	0.84	0.76	0.62	0.86	0.72	0.65	0.85
SVC	0.67	0.75	0.58	0.71	0.76	0.89	0.29	0.89	0.70	0.41	0.82
KNN	0.64	0.76	0.57	0.58	0.82	0.76	0.48	0.70	0.65	0.53	0.76
Decision tree	0.73	0.73	0.65	0.70	0.86	0.73	0.62	0.86	0.69	0.65	0.86
Naïve Bayes	0.57	0.57	0.49	0.50	0.84	0.93	0.23	0.61	0.65	0.32	0.71

For each model, confusion matrices were plotted to visualize the distribution of correctly and incorrectly classified instances. The models generally experienced challenges differentiating between low- and mid-risk cases. This is an indication that pregnancies with a medium level of risk might be difficult to detect and special attention should be paid by medical personnel not to dismiss any signs of a problem. From figure 7, the high-risk class was relatively easier to detect, likely because of significantly high blood sugar and blood pressure levels among women in this class, making it easy to identify risks.

Figure 7: Confusion matrices for the 6 models

4.0 DISCUSSION

In this study, the use of ML algorithms showed a good performance for predicting maternal risk levels. The accuracy and AUC scores of the Random Forest model were superior to those of other prediction algorithms. In addition, blood sugar level was determined to be a major variable for predicting pregnancy risk levels.

High blood sugar during pregnancy, or gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), is a common cause of pregnancy complications that is becoming more prevalent in modern times (Shi et al., 2020). It is therefore no surprise that blood sugar level is the variable in our dataset that exhibits the highest positive correlation with pregnancy risk level. According to Kin et al. (2021), GDM is prevalent in 5-25.5% of pregnancies worldwide and varies according to race, age, and body composition (body percentage of fat, bone, and muscle). This makes it imperative that healthcare professionals pay close attention to the blood sugar levels of expectant mothers from the first trimester to anticipate any complications that might develop later.

The random forest (RF) algorithm is a refinement of the decision tree. Specifically, it is the aggregation of the output of multiple decision trees to introduce non-linearity and therefore robustness to noise in the input data (Rigatti, 2017). Its strength lies in its ability to discover non-linear interactions between features and targets, making it ideal for medical problems where targets are subject to complex interactions between the predictors. This ability explains how the RF algorithm performed better than other models used in this study by finding a way to distinguish

between the low- and mid-risk cases, a task which proved to be difficult for the other algorithms due to the similarities between predictor values in both classes.

This study, however, has several limitations. First, the data collected mainly accounted for women between ages 21 and 30. This implies that children and adolescents between ages 10-20 and women older than 35 may be at higher risks of developing complications, but this cannot be accounted for because the data collection process was biased. Second, as recommended by Rigatti (2017), performing hyperparameter tuning using methods like grid search and random search could improve the performance of all the algorithms employed in this study. Other machine learning techniques like cross validation can also be employed on future studies to give a more accurate measure of model performance.

5.0 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, using machine learning to predict pregnancy risk levels is feasible, particularly for high-risk pregnancies. This is useful for early detection of pregnancy risks and will facilitate pre-labour decisions such as delivery mode. The random forest algorithm performs well for this classification problem and can be used on its own or in an ensemble with other models to predict pregnancy risk levels.

REFERENCES

- Bertini, A., Salas, R., Chabert, S., Sobrevia, L., & Pardo, F. (2022). Using machine learning to predict complications in pregnancy: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9, 1385.
- Boateng, E. Y., & Abaye, D. A. (2019). A review of the logistic regression model with emphasis on medical research. *Journal of data analysis and information processing*, 7(04), 190.
- Chen, L., Shi, L., Chao, M. S., Tong, X., & Wang, F. (2020). Stressful life events, hypertensive disorders, and high blood sugar during pregnancy. *Stress and Health*, 36(2), 160-165.
- Cleveland Clinic. (2021, December 14). High-risk pregnancy. Retrieved April 10, 2023, from <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/22190-high-risk-pregnancy>
- Cunningham, P., & Delany, S. J. (2021). K-nearest neighbour classifiers-a tutorial. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 54(6), 1-25.
- Darcy, A. M., Louie, A. K., & Roberts, L. W. (2016). Machine learning and the profession of medicine. *JAMA*, 315(6), 551–552. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.18421>
- Hinton, G. (2018). Deep learning—a technology with the potential to transform health care. *JAMA*, 320(11), 1101–1102. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2018.11100>
- Islam, M. N., Mahmud, T., Khan, N. I., Mustafina, S. N., & Islam, A. N. (2020). Exploring machine learning algorithms to find the best features for predicting modes of childbirth. *IEEE Access*, 9, 1680–1692.
- Kim, H. Y., Kim, J., Noh, E., Ahn, K. H., Cho, G. J., Hong, S. C., ... & Kim, H. J. (2021). Prepregnancy hemoglobin levels and gestational diabetes mellitus in pregnancy. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 171, 108608.
- Makary, M. A., & Daniel, M. (2016). Medical error—the third leading cause of death in the US. *BMJ*, 353. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i2139>

- Obermeyer, Z., & Emanuel, E. J. (2016). Predicting the future—big data, machine learning, and clinical medicine. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 375, 1216–1219. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp1606181>
- Pisner, D. A., & Schnyer, D. M. (2020). Support vector machine. In *Machine learning* (pp. 101-121). Academic Press.
- Rigatti, S. J. (2017). Random forest. *Journal of Insurance Medicine*, 47(1), 31-39.
- Tomar, K.; Sharma, C.M.; Sharma, P.; Gupta, D.; Chariar, V.M. Impacts of Environmental Factors on Maternal Health in Low Resource Settings. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Resources and Environment Sciences (ICRES 2024)*, Bangkok, Thailand, 7–9 June 2024. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- US National Institutes of Health. (2017, January 31). What is a high-risk pregnancy? Retrieved April 10, 2023, from <https://www.nichd.nih.gov/health/topics/pregnancy/conditioninfo/high-risk>
- World Health Organization. (2023). A woman dies every two minutes due to pregnancy or childbirth: UN agencies. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news/item/a-woman-dies-every-two-minutes-due-to-pregnancy-or-childbirth>.
- Yang, F. J. (2018, December). An implementation of naive bayes classifier. In *2018 International conference on computational science and computational intelligence (CSCI)* (pp. 301-306). IEEE.